

RELEVANT TOOLS FOR ABILITY LEVERAGE OF DISABLED STUDENTS IN NIGERIAN TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract

This study examined relevant tools to leverage abilities in the disabled Nigerian students in tertiary institutions. There has been challenges facing the disabled in institution of higher learning due to their various and varied impairment. They are therefore subjected to handicapping conditions quite unlike their non-disabled counterparts. This study sought to find relevant tools to improve on those challenges. The tools that can be utilized for the leverage of ability of the disabled are goal setting and time management. It is on the above premise that the theories of goal setting and time management are showcased: implication, relationship and application of each on abilities of the disabled are revealed. The conclusion was reached that both strategies are capable of leveraging abilities of disabled Nigerians. It is on the above premise that it was recommended among others that the skills be made available to the disabled in Nigeria by the appropriate resource persons.

Introduction

There are challenges in the education of students that are disabled in Nigeria. Several policies and strategies have been put in place to better the lots of this special population. These are evidenced in National Policy on education that dates back to 1977 through 2013. These attempts remained the hope for the hopeless and hapless disabled. No doubt these individual are found in institutions of higher learning where they are faced with

disabled. There is axiom that if disability has not met you it has not left you. It is another way of saying that any person can become disabled at any age, there it behooves on all to care for the disabled. This suggests that assistance to any disabled is that given to self or relations. There is many students in institution of higher learning that are disabled. They are faced with challenges that consume their ability and require setting goals and follow dateline and deadline. There is a popular saying that there is ability in disability. That shows that there abound latent ability in every disabled.. This parlance is also interpreted to mean that every disabled has ability the only challenge is how to identify it. Akin to that is identification and utilization of to that can a go a long way to leverage the abilities in the disabled.

It is therefore imperativeness of the tools to serve the above purpose that raised the curiosity of the present researcher. It is our belief that there abounds ability in every disabled person. It is important for the remaining ability to be sought for in every disabled one and be made to serve utility function for the disabled. There has been frantic effort made in rehabilitation programme. Rehabilitation is returning disabled one to normalcy or as near normalcy as is possible (Obi, 2010). There is special education which Federal Republic Nigeria 2013 conceived as customized education for persons that cannot benefit from general education. These are popular ventures or scenario for the disabled to showcase the ability in their disability. There is need for complementing the foregoing.

The obvious lacuna is what relevant efforts are made by and for the disabled to complement and supplement the forgoing lee ways. This is where crux of the matter lies. The disabled are therefore expected to look inwards to better their future. Exposure of the disabled to Goal setting and Time management seem to be a popular venture towards helping this special population. These tools should be utilized. According to Encarta (2009) tools are devices designed to do specific kind of workHornby(2015) perceived utilization as making use of something in effective way. There is need to utilize the tools to leverage the ability of the disabled. Encarta (2009) viewed leverage as power to get things done or an advantage one is bound to have and be able to utilize. The disabled are already impaired and as such handicapped. In Nigeria, tertiary institutions lack all it takes to educate the disabled in terms of facilities, equipment, personnel among others. Moreover, this special population

with special needs. These are unique needs required to make up to be able to forge ahead in life. That is why they are regarded as exceptional hence they differ or deviate from what is considered normal or conventional. Disability limits one's ability. Hornby (2015) viewed ability as physical or mental power or skill to do something. This lack or loss of ability has ever remained the bane of the disabled. The ways to impact on the residual ability of the disabled has remained a challenge that made this study imperative. That is why it is interested in what can leverage the ability of the disabled Nigerians in institution of higher learning.

There was a quasi-experimental study carried out by Eke (2006) on the effect of selected coping strategies on the academic stress of the pupils with visual impairment in special education centre Oji River, Enugu state. It was found in the study that the use of the selected copying strategies significantly eased off the academic stress of pupils with visual impairment in the experimental group as against the control group not exposed to the treatment. Eke, thereafter, recommended that the strategies should be exposed to all the categories of disability. It is in this wise that the present study is deemed imperative considering the fact that the disabled generally face various challenges in tertiary institutions. This is why it became inevitable to uncover tools that the utilization shall go a long way to leverage the abilities of the disabled. The tools in question are goal setting and time management. The study was therefore considered apt.

The Tools- Goal Setting and Time Management

Goal setting is an important method of deciding what one wants to achieve in one's life, separating what is important from what is irrelevant, or a distraction, motivating self. It is building for self-confidence, based on successful achievement of goals. Goal setting is much more than simply saying that one wants something to happen. Unless one clearly defines what one wants, and understands why one wants in the first place. Success is considerably reduced. By following certain rules, Goal setting is powerful because it provides focus and shapes our dreams and gives us the ability to hone in on the exact action one needs to perform to achieve everything one desires in life. Goals are great because they cause one to stretch and grow in ways that one never has before in order to reach one's goals one must become better

Time management is another tool. Wikipedia (2014) defined time management as the act or process of planning and exercising conscious control over the amount of time spent on specific activities, especially to increase effectiveness, efficiency or productivity. One is guided by activities that are important and urgent that differ from those that are neither urgent nor important though cases abound where certain activities are important yet not urgent. Time management refers to managing one's time effectively so that the right time is allocated to the right activity. It plays vital role in our personal lives. Agulana in Eke (2006) noted that time is raw material of which life is made and that time is highly perishable, irreplaceable, irreversible and irretrievable. Agulana asserted that one has to be able to utilize time for the attainment of one's objectives.

The acquisition of these two tools are needed but lacking among the Nigerian disabled students in tertiary institutions. It is therefore imperative to visit the theories of goal setting and time management and establish how the disabled can use them to complement and supplement all other ventures that can help themselves in life. It is proper to unveil the theories of goal setting and time management and establish their implication,

relationship and application of each in leveraging abilities of the disabled Nigerians in tertiary institutions.

Goal Setting Models

Goal setting was propounded by J.D. Krumbolt in 1966 (Eke, 2006). The author was a humanist psychologist and renowned behaviourist. The author crafted the model in steps which are to be observed to make for goal setting.

The first step is identifying and defining problem. This is done in specific behavioural terms. In a bid to do this, counseling skills as acceptance, listening, clarifying and questioning are used. With this, the origin of the problem is discovered. It is studied for specific definition. The problem then becomes defined in this very step.

The second procedure is setting goals. These goals are usually derived from the problem. The major goals are reduced to sub-goals in two ways by graduation and looking at factors that trigger the problems and setting goals to eliminate their influence. Setting goals give direction treatment (solution) problem. The third procedure is selecting the techniques for the treatment. The method to be used is briefly explained. Out of many methods, best choice to adopt is made especially effective ones not those that are injurious, exploitative and dehumanizing.

The fourth procedure is the treatment itself. How to carry out the treatment which is solution process is disclosed the roles, rigors needed to complete the treatment etc. This phase comprises a number of sections, practice and practical exercise aimed at alleviating or overcoming the problem.

The fifth stage is evaluation and correction. Formative evaluation is used to build corrective measures into treatment. Feedback information from assignment is used to evaluate the extent of improvement, difficulties and factors retarding progress are addressed hence measures are found to eliminate them. Summative evaluation is used to find out the extent one has achieved the main goals. This is done immediately after treatment stage.

The last procedure is follow up. The aim is to investigate the extent to which one has been able to retain the behaviours he acquired or goals he achieved on the termination of treatment. This can be implemented long after the termination. This can be done through the use of interview, questionnaire, observation or test and inventories to collect data for the follow up exercise. The result indicates the extent the solution has been successful. It indicates whether the client an individual will need booster treatment to strengthen the behavior acquired or not.

Implication, Relationship and the Application of the Tool

The disabled are so identified due to impairment that invariably subject to handicap. Goal setting is applicable to Nigerian disabled hence they are faced with impairment that subject them to handicapping conditions. These are all considered as problems and therefore to handle this, approach to utilization of goal setting becomes imperative. They can identify the source, origin or the rein forcers of the handicapping conditions. This could be academic or other related tasks. This is then followed by setting goals derived from the problem in a bid to overcome or solve it or come to terms with them. Later, techniques for the solution or treatment are selected. The methods are explained to them or efforts made by them to understand it. The next one is actual implementation which is actual solution exercise or treatment process by the disabled. There is an axiom that

overcome handicaps resulting from impairment. The one that follows suit is the disabled evaluating their set objectives. That is to note whether the goals set are achieved. This can be when the treatment is on or after the treatment. Follow up exercise affirms whether or not goals setting served utility function for the disabled. If otherwise something should be done. From the foregoing, in view of gamut of handicaps that the disabled are prone to, the way out to a large extent is goal setting. The goal setting promises leveraging handicaps of the disabled.

Time Management- The Seven Maxims of Time Management

Seven maxims of time management were propounded by Wilson Wilson (2003). Wilson used seven steps to carry out the theory. The step one is simplicity. This implies a prescription for time digestion. Here, Wilson disclosed that one should own less, do less and say no. This means when one is faced with activities and time lag, one should take the few activities one can do and ignore others by way of saying NO to things one cannot do considering the time factor or time lag. The step two is organized which Wilson conceptualized as out of sight, out of mind and out of the way. Wilson disclosed that activities now selected should be organized. The author supported having time and a place for everything and doing everything at its time and place. This now affects those not ignored, things one owns hence to one they are indispensable and can handle that without strain. He remarked that if otherwise stress is induced.

The step three is balance which implies keeping things harmonious and balanced with time. Everything is allotted time and deadline proposed to be followed suit, not allowing procrastination. The step four is priorities which imply that things which matter most, must never be at the mercy of things which matter least. He perceived this as the most philosophical part of the seven steps. Here, it is not about squeezing as much minutes into the days as possible but about locating space for important things first after which the less important things be considered. This means to consider mainly what is needed.

The step five is aim that means one using time should be ready, aim and fire. This means recognizing the steps accordingly. Indecision or procrastination is not allowed. There is protection of one's prime time which is the time one performs optimally. The sixth step is structure, which is building the infrastructure for habitual action. Here the plan is put into action. Time is pragmatically utilized. Wilson disclosed that to achieve the foregoing, one has to plan monthly at the best ending of each month. Invest time in planning session for the upcoming month. Schedule should be done weekly at the end of each week preferably Sunday nights. Priorities should be on ground daily at the end of each day's service in a bid to determine the next days' time table. He advised following pareto's principle called the vital few and trivial many which is concentration on few important things and ignore many irrelevant or unimportant things. Agulana in Eke(2006) used the term radical surgery on the trivial irrelevant things which is cutting off those minor ones. Attention and focus are on the actualization of plan within known time lag

The seventh step is habituate which is a key component to successful time management that emphasizes taking proven approaches and makes time management as habit. Wilson disclosed that the best way to it is not forgetting on every occasion to ask oneself things one is doing now not one of the unnecessary things. He likened time to the coin of one's life and one needs to spend it wisely. Similarly Agulana in Eke (2016)

advocated that occasionally one should question oneself what one does with time. One may discover it is a waste of time. This emphasizes being used to the seven maxims of time management.

Implication, Relationship and the Application of the Tool

The seven maxims of time management could be used to leveraging the handicaps of the disabled Nigeria. Time is precious and should be managed. Agulana in Eke (2006) once reported that time is what man wants to kill but it turns to kill man. This is very related to the disabled more so when challenged by impairment and handicaps. The disabled can apply the seven maxim of Wilson to leverage their handicaps. They can apply each of the steps in their schedules. They can simplify by considering time and activities they can handle while they say No! to those ones that they cannot accommodate. The remaining ones are organized and later balanced each according to time lag and place of execution recognizing deadlines. Things or activities are then prioritized. One gets ready, aim and structure activities into action to agree with time that allows no room for indecision and procrastination. The disabled could learn to plan, schedule and prioritize activities with time available. This could be done by asking themselves question about what they the disabled are doing at any point in time so as to ensure that time is not wasted such that before long time management becomes habit to them and they be able to use it joyfully, artistically and effortlessly in their academic and other life endeavors.

Conclusion

The disabled Nigeria students in tertiary institutions seem to face endless challenges. That apart, the attitudes towards them seem to worsen their condition. It was worse for those disabled that have given up trials on ground of the handicap and disabilities arising from their impairments. Some of them that challenge their challenges are better off. Notwithstanding the attitude of the society towards the disabled remains their bane. Olayi. E (personal communication, 20th September, 2016) regretting the way his abilities was not recognized asserted that his then boss looked more on his disability and not what he did or could do. It is said that there is ability in disability. It is reawakening such spirit in the disabled, those that have something to do with them and the society that this study became imperative. The disabled should be counseled to have that in back of their minds that lots of hope abounds. It is germane to turn their stress to eustress, stumbling blocks from impairment to stepping stones generating from their latent abilities. The obstacles of handicaps of these special students shall then be replaced by the opportunities garnered (upon utilization) from these relevant tools. The father of stress, Selye in Eke (2006) referred eustress to as good stress that which one does with joy hence effortless and result oriented. The exposure of the Nigerian disabled students to goal setting and time management shall spring many surprises in their endeavors in life (be it academics or others). The foregoing is advocated as leeways to leverage the abilities in the disabled Nigeria to supplement and complement whatever come their way as aids. belated policy impl

References

- Ajobiewe, T (2014) *Managing Disability in the Family and Community* (2nd ed.). Ibadan. Tetoni Education series
- Eke, V.U.(2000). *Elements of Special Education and the Exceptional child*.Nsukka; AP. Publisher.
- Eke, V.U.(2006). Effect of selected coping strategies of the academic stress of pupils with visual impairment in special education centre Oji River Enugu state. *An Unpublished Ph.D Thesis of University of Nigeria Nsukka.*
- Encarta (2009). *Dictionary*. Accessed 21/09/16
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013). *National Policy on Education*. Yaba-Lagos: NERDC
- Hornby, A.S.(2015). *Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary*. Oxford: University Press.
- Obi, F.B.(2010) *Essential of Special Needs*. Calabar: Kp. Klentin Printer/Publisher.
- Wikipedia (2014). *Encyclopedia*. Retrieved 21/09/16